

CAL FRESH PARTICIPATION RATE AMONG FOOD INSECURE CSUF STUDENTS

by

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Food insecurity is a prevalent health condition in many countries worldwide. This issue affects many communities in the United States, including college students. The United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) describes food insecurity as "a lack of consistent access to enough food for an active, healthy life" (U.S. Department of Agriculture, 2022). Food insecurity describes the irregular accessibility to nutrient-dense foods, which affects their health. In 2006, the USDA introduced different ranges of food insecurity to assess households' food security; two ranges of food insecurity are low food security and very low security. Low food insecurity is defined as someone who reports a decrease in quality and variety in their diets but indicates little to no reduced food intake (U.S. Department of Agriculture, 2022). Very low food security reports constant disrupted eating patterns and reduced food intake (U.S. Department of Agriculture, 2022). Food insecurity has been a health concern for generations in the United States. In 2021, the USDA reported that 10.2 percent (13.5 million) households experienced food insecurity sometime during that year (U.S. Department of Agriculture, 2022). The higher percentage of Americans struggling to meet their basic needs can be rooted in complex socioeconomic factors. Some causes of food insecurity are correlated to poverty, unemployment, lack of affordable housing, low income, and systematic racism (Feeding America, 2022). These factors, in a sense, correlate and increase a person's risk of food insecurity. Low income, lay-offs, or other stressors could result in an individual being forced to pay bills than purchasing food. As the prevalence of this issue remains, questions arise about its connection and health.

Food insecurity in college students has gained attention over the past years as a critical public health issue. In 2019, a systematic review identified that food insecurity is three times (43%) more prevalent in college students than the average U.S. adult household (13%) (Nazmi et al., 2019). Food insecurity in college students can be caused by specific factors that pertain to

higher education. Examples of possible reasons for this issue are high tuition and fees, unaffordable housing, and limited financial aid (Esaryk et al., 2022). Food insecurity has a significant impact on an individual's health. Due to the lack of adequate food, students face adverse health outcomes such as depression, cognitive problems, anemia, and possible congenital disabilities (Gunderson & Ziliak 2015). Food insecurity threatens not only students' health but also their academic success. Inconsistent meals and a lack of nutrients have a connection to student success. The links between success and food insecurity include lower concentration, energy, and student retention (Morris, Smith, Davis, & Null, 2016). According to a study, researchers discovered the association between academics and food insecurity to be constant and precise. Researchers learned that "food insecure students are about three times less likely to be among the highest 10% GPA compared to their food secure counterparts" (Weaver et al., 2020, p. 730). The inability to focus and lack of energy impacts GPAs and the possible threat of degree completion. Food insecure students face the physical impact of inadequate food and time used to secure food, impeding academic success. In a university population, food insecurity appears more prevalent among specific communities. Black or Hispanic students are more likely to become food insecure (Bruening, van Woerden, Todd, & Laska, 2016). Food insecurity is also prevalent in younger students, low-income, employed, receiving financial aid, and housing insecure (El Zein et al., 2019). These features of college students have increased their risk of facing food insecurity during the COVID-19 pandemic. Students who are employed part-time or full-time were affected by the impact of the pandemic, especially those in the service industry (United States Department of Labor Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2020). During the COVID-19 Pandemic, Americans received federal stimulus checks as a part of the COVID-19 relief package.

According to the US Department of Treasury, most college students were considered ineligible to receive a stimulus check due to being filed as dependent on their parents' tax returns (United States Department of Treasury, 2020). Due to loss of employment, school closures, and lack of federal assistance, college students encountered challenges in acquiring food. Some students who relied on university dining were forced to purchase and make their meals which is a challenge due to a lack of food knowledge and even an inability to cook (Owens et al., 2020). Food insecurity remains prevalent in college populations due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic (Rosales, 2021). Universities have addressed the rising numbers of college students who are food insecure through various programs and assistance.

In California, many universities have implemented a food pantry to distribute nutrient-dense foods that fulfill students' needs at no cost. Institutions such as California State University, Northridge, University of California, Berkeley, and San Diego Mesa College have implemented various food assistance programs such as food drives and food pantries to address food insecurity within their student population (Rosales, 2021). California State University, Fullerton, recently opened its food pantry in 2021. In the past year, the program has served 4,974 enrolled students by providing free groceries and addressing the rising food insecurity issue by providing workshops and access to public assistance programs outside the campus (ASI, 2022).

Cal Fresh

There are many assistive programs available to help struggling students with food security, one of them being Cal Fresh. Cal Fresh is the state of California's version of the federal food assistance program, Supplemental Nutrition Assistance Program (SNAP). This public assistance program "provides monthly food benefits to individuals and families with low income and provides economic benefits to communities" (California Department of Social Services,

2022). Cal Fresh applicants must meet specific criteria in order to receive assistance.

Households applying for Cal Fresh must provide information regarding citizenship/immigration status, income, work requirements, etc. (California Department of Social Services, 2022). Cal Fresh households are categorically eligible through gross monthly income. The maximum gross income for households is 200% of the Federal Poverty Level (California Department of Social Services, 2022).

In regard to college students, the Cal Fresh requirements must be met as well as meeting additional requirements. To be considered, individuals must be between the ages of 18 – 49, enrolled in an institute of higher-education, physically and mentally fit, and must be enrolled in at least half-time regular curriculum (courses that meet standards for graduation requirements) (California Department of Social Services, 2022). Cal Fresh also requires specific work requirements to be eligible. Cal Fresh asks applicants to take part of certain employment and training activities such as “searching for work, performing community service, or going to school or training” (California Department of Social Services, 2022). Student applicants must meet work exemptions such as having an on-campus job, work an average 20 hours a week, and approved for state or federal work-study (California Department of Social Services, 2022). This updated work exemption has helped college students specifically with enrollment. Students have faced issues with the work requirements due to their demanding academics and other commitments (Rosales, 2021).

When enrolled in the program, the benefits of Cal Fresh provide help when buying nutritious foods at grocery stores and farmers' markets. Eligible student applicants receive benefits depending on criteria such as their school enrollment and work hours; monthly benefits are issued through an Electronic Benefit Transfer (EBT) card (California Department of Social

Services, 2022). Single students enrolled in Cal Fresh can receive up to \$250 monthly for groceries (Rosales, 2021). With these benefits, individuals can purchase nutritious foods at any grocery store. Cal Fresh enables to stretch their food budgets which allows participants to afford healthier foods (California Department of Social Services, 2022).

When SNAP was first designed to address food insecurity, there was a need for more focus on the college community. According to the US Department of Agriculture, the federal policy first stated that students were ineligible for SNAP benefits (US Department of Agriculture, 2020). This rule was enacted in 1977, during the restructuring of higher education. During this time, the funding for free public higher education was expanding significantly to where people of low income and color could attend college (Taylor, 2020). Federal legislators made these restrictions during the time of change in higher education, assuming that all students have financial support from their families (Treisman, 2020). The result of this enactment left 200,000 college students losing their SNAP benefits (Roberts, 1981). When these restrictions were enacted, policymakers had another assumption that "if a student did not have familial support, they would either be working or they would apply for public assistance" (Dickinson, 2021). They included exemptions for low-income students to qualify for food stamps such as working 20 hours a week, being on public assistance, having a child no older than 12, having no access to childcare, being disabled, being enrolled in a federal work-study program, or being enrolled in an employment training program (Dickinson, 2021).

Today, many college students, especially in California, are disqualified from receiving SNAP/Cal Fresh benefits. One of the primary reasons for students not qualifying is due to the SNAP requirement of working 20 hours a week or more (Owens et al., 2020). The time exemption has been reported as difficult to meet due to the time commitment of being a full-time

student and participating in extracurricular activities (Chavarian-Rivas, Doherty & Dizon-Ross, 2021). A majority of students who do work part-time, work for the service industry such as restaurants, bars, and healthcare. During the COVID-19 pandemic, a lot of students faced job losses which resulted in them not qualifying for Cal Fresh (Owens et al., 2021). As time progressed, the exemption was later adjusted to meet these concerns. In response to the pandemic, Cal Fresh currently has waived the work requirement in counties for people who only receive Cal Fresh and do not have minor children until June 23, 2023 (CDSS, 2022). During the pandemic, Assemblyman Jesse Gabriel introduced a bill that expanded the work exemption so more students can qualify for Cal Fresh. Assembly Bill 396 was approved on October 4, 2021. It requires campus-based programs at California Community Colleges, and California State Universities to submit an application to the Department of Social Services to be certified as a program that students can utilize to meet the work exemption (AB 396, 2021). Students employed under the certified program are qualified to apply to Cal Fresh and receive benefits. These campus-based programs consist of internships, apprenticeships, or tutoring seminars (Rosales, 2021).

Although Cal Fresh has expanded accessibility to the program, college students face different barriers to enrolling. Only 43% of college students eligible for SNAP are enrolled (Dickinson, 2021). There tends to be hesitation for college students to apply due to stigma associated with public assistance, the time needed for the application process, and fear of public charge (Chavarin-Rivas et al., 2021). Students who are immigrants or live with immigrant parents assume they must share household information that could negatively impact their non-citizen family (Chavarin-Rivas et al., 2021). Undocumented students and families hesitate to apply for public assistance due to fear of public charge (Chavarin-Rivas et al., 2021). Public

charge is an individual who depends on long-term governmental support; immigrants who are deemed a public charge will lose their ability to apply for legal status in the U.S. (California Department of Social Services, 2022). Misinformation or lack of awareness prevents immigrant households and students from receiving food insecurity assistance. In reality, undocumented individuals will not become a public charge when using Cal Fresh and will not affect their chances of receiving a green card nor affect their or their family's immigration status (California Department of Social Services, 2022). Cal Fresh has been implementing marketing strategies to educate undocumented students to debunk any misinformation that is preventing them from applying.

When applying to SNAP, students also face the stigma associated with public assistance. Food-insecure students tend to have feelings of unworthiness when applying for public assistance, that there are people in more need than they are (Chavarian-Rivas et al., 2021). When some students apply for SNAP and are approved, they associate public assistance with shame and embarrassment (Chavarian-Rivas et al., 2021). There is a stigma associated with SNAP participation. The younger population perceives that the people who use SNAP are always associated with a poorer community, stereotypes within a race, and overall negativity (Chavarian-Rivas et al., 2021). Students feel ashamed around their peers when using Electronic Benefits Transfer (EBT) in a public setting and fear judgment when peers discover that they have financial needs (Chavarian-Rivas et al., 2021). Stigma associated with SNAP results in students having anxiety around experiencing humiliation and judgment. These consequences can be a barrier for students to hesitate to use their benefits and apply for food assistance.

Alongside the stigma, the SNAP application process is complex and lengthy, which can prevent students from applying (Chavarian-Rivas et al., 2021). The application process requires

multiple documents and steps to be considered eligible. County workers have reported that the student eligibility application consists of more complicated criteria compared to non-student applications; this process leaves students unsure about specific documentation, what residence to use, and parent information (Chavarian-Rivas, Doherty & Dizon-Ross, 2021). Alongside the application process, students also face the barrier of the overall administration process. The long lines at county offices, lack of knowledge to recertify their Cal Fresh, and lack of application assistance result in students no longer continuing the process, being too intimidated to start, and dropping out of Cal Fresh entirely (Chavarian-Rivas et al., 2021). The barriers and stigma associated with applying for and using public assistance are prevalent among food-insecure students.

Impact of participating in Cal Fresh on college food insecurity, health and academic measures

Students utilizing Cal Fresh benefits provide prevention and improvement on student wellness. A recent study wanted to investigate the impact of Cal Fresh on college food insecurity. With a quasi-experimental study, the authors hypothesized that food insecurity in college students would decrease among students who were enrolled in Cal Fresh (Nazmi et al., 2022). The results indicated that food insecurity decreased by 63% among enrolled Cal Fresh students (Nazmi et al., 2022). This study found that participating in Cal Fresh reduced college food insecurity. The authors also noted that an additional possibility for this reduction was students utilizing their university's food pantries and a meal voucher program (Nazmi et al., 2022). The authors then concluded that food insecurity decreases significantly among students enrolled in Cal Fresh during their academic years (Nazmi et al., 2022). Being enrolled in Cal Fresh could then also possibly contribute to improving not only student health but their overall academic achievement.

With Cal Fresh benefits, students have more access to nutrient-dense foods. Nutritious foods have a significant influence on academics. Students facing food insecurity often experience multiple deficiencies in protein, carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals (Just, 2019). Vitamin E, B, iodine, and zinc are correlated with cognitive abilities and mental concentration (Chenoweth, 2007). Also, a good intake of amino acids and carbohydrates shows improvement in perception, intuition, and reasoning (Lieberman, 2003). With the utilization of Cal Fresh, students can obtain access to these essential nutrients.

Efforts by California Colleges to address food insecurity

California college campuses are encouraging students to utilize Cal Fresh benefits. California State Universities have been promoting this program through their on-campus resources. Cal State Long Beach, Chico, and Fullerton target their student populations by providing outreach programs, having Cal Fresh recruiters help students apply for the program through webinars and social media, and university outreach (Salgado, 2021). Cal State Long Beach expanded their Cal Fresh outreach team by using their Cal Fresh grant money to hire a full-time coordinator and some graduate assistants (Salgado, 2021). With the expansion of their team, students are able to access this service more easily. Long Beach's program has implemented a real-time chat box to answer any questions when a student visits their website and has added summer drop-in hours to learn about Cal Fresh (Salgado, 2021). Cal State Long Beach has reported that they have seen an increase of student enrollment over the past 2020 school year (Salgado, 2021). Cal State Fullerton, dedicates every Wednesday for Cal Fresh representatives to table outside the university's food pantry (ASI, 2022). Fullerton's basic needs program dedicates their efforts to enrolling more of their students into the Cal Fresh program. They have recently uploaded a new Cal Fresh website where students can navigate how the application

process works and can fill out a pre-screen eligibility form (Division of Student Affairs, 2022). These efforts by the universities an opportunity for students to become aware of other resources available to address their need.

Methods

This research project investigated the CalFresh participation rate among food insecure CSUF students and their sociodemographic characteristics. For this study, we collected data from the Pandemic Impact on CSUF Students Study. This study was conducted through an online survey during the beginning of the COVID-19 Pandemic. The survey was first distributed to CSUF students in June, 2020; a follow-up survey was sent out a year later in April, 2021. In this study, food insecurity was determined by the USDA's 10-item U.S. Adult food Security Survey (US Department of Agriculture, 2022). A student would be considered food insecure if they experienced food insecurity either early in the pandemic or a year later.

CalFresh participation was self-reported. Students were considered to participate in CalFresh if they participated at one or more time points in 2020-2021. To examine differences in CalFresh participation among food insecure students by sociodemographic characteristics, Chi-square tests were conducted using SPSS.

Results

As shown in Table 1, the majority of our sample were Hispanic (48.2%) and Asian (20.9%). 61.8% of students are twenty four years or younger and 29.6% work part-time.

As seen in Table 2, 33% of CSUF students are food insecure and of those food insecure, 20% reported participating in CalFresh. Differences in CalFresh participation by age, parental status, and Pell Grant status were statistically significant. From our results, students 24 years old

and younger have a lower participation rate compared to those over 24. Students with children have a higher participation rate compared to those with no children. There were also differences with race and ethnicity. For example, Asian and Hispanic students were less likely to participate compared to non-Hispanic Whites. However, these results were not statistically significant.

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics of food insecure students (n=110)

	<i>% (n)</i>
Age	
= < 24 years	61.8% (68)
25-29 years	10.9% (12)
30-39 years	16.4% (18)
= > 40 years	10.9% (12)
Gender	
Male	20% (22)
Female	79.1% (87)
Level of Education	
Undergraduate	87.3% (96)
Graduate	12.7% (14)
Transfer students	
Transfer	44.9% (48)
Not a transfer	55.1% (59)
Race/ethnicity	
White	12.7% (14)
Black	8.2% (9)
Asian	20.9% (23)
Hispanic	48.2% (53)
MENA	6.4% (7)
Other	3.6% (4)
Parent Status	
Has Children	16.4% (18)
No Children	83.6% (92)
Pell Grant Status	
Pell Grant	48.1% (51)
No Pell Grant	51.9% (55)
Work status	
Part-time	25.5% (28)
Full-time	11.8% (13)
Unemployed	52.8% (58)
Other	10% (11)

Table 2. CalFresh participation among food insecure students by sociodemographic characteristics

	% (n)
Age ($p \geq .038$)	
=< 24 years	12.3%
25-29 years	16.7%
30-39 years	27.8%
= > 40 years	41.6%
Gender	
Male	14.3%
Female	21.2%
Level of Education	
Undergraduate	20.4%
Graduate	14.2%
Transfer students	
Transfer	68.4% (33)
Not a transfer	51.4% (30)
Race/ethnicity	
White, Non-Hispanic	21.4%
Black, Non-Hispanic	62.5%
Asian	8.7%
Hispanic	19.2%
MENA	0%
Other	33.3%
Parent Status ($p \geq .002$)	
Has Children	44.4%
No children	14.6%
Pell Grant Status ($p \geq .05$)	
Pell Grant	31.3%
No Pell Grant	35.7%
Work status	
Part-time	29.6%
Full-time	7.7%
Unemployed	16%

Discussion

From our sample, we discovered that 33% of CSUF students are food insecure and of those food insecure, 20% reported participating in CalFresh. We then looked at differences in

rates of CalFresh participation varied by students' sociodemographic characteristics. With the statistically significant characteristics, students who were 24 years old or younger were less likely to participate in CalFresh compared to older students. Students who were parents or are a recipient of the Pell Grant were more likely to participate in Cal Fresh. We noticed differences in other characteristics such as race and gender. For example, males were less likely to participate than females and students who identified as Hispanic, Asian, or MENA had the lowest participation rates. Although we noticed these differences, these characteristics were not statistically significant.

From the literature background, some barriers students face when applying to Cal Fresh consist of qualification factors or stigmas associated with receiving government assistance. From our findings, we can associate the low rates of participation in younger students with the stigmas associated with CalFresh. Younger students in college are still adjusting and learning about themselves; how they're perceived by society is very vital to them. This mindset approach can be an influencing factor on why younger students have a lower participation rate. As discussed in the literature background, students who come from immigrant families, specifically Hispanic students, hesitate to apply for CalFresh due to the fear of exposing their or their family's immigration status. From our results, Hispanic students had one of the lowest participatory rates. Factors such as immigration status could be an influence in their participation in CalFresh. More research needs to be conducted to investigate why specific groups have lower participation and provide findings that'll help address and improve participation rates.

Some limitations of this study was that we had a small sample size which could've prevented some findings from being more reliable. Although our study was longitudinal which served as a strength in our data analysis. Another strength was our collection of data and the food

insecurity and CalFresh participation was measured from two time points. Lastly the use of multiple sociodemographic measures to examine potential inequities in CSUF improved our data analysis.

Conclusion

Food insecurity is prevalent throughout many communities in the United States. Overall, food insecurity disproportionately affects college students. It is important to address this issue because due to lack of nutrients, students face cognitive barriers which affects their academic success and experience. With this study, we identified and analyzed the participation rates among different sociodemographic characteristics. With the results, further research is needed to investigate the reasons why students of certain sociodemographic characteristics are not participating or if they face other barriers such as meeting Cal Fresh requirements. Till then, California State University, Fullerton and other universities should encourage participation among their population and promote resources to address this issue.

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